

**ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ДИНАМІКИ ПОКАЗНИКІВ ДЕПРЕСІЇ І ЯКОСТІ
ЖИТТЯ У ХВОРИХ З ПАРОКСИЗМАЛЬНОЮ ФОРМОЮ ФІБРИЛЯЦІЇ
ПЕРЕДСЕРДЬ**

**SPECIFICS DYNAMICS INDICATORS OF DEPRESSION AND QUALITY
OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH PAROXYSMIC FORM OF ATRIAL
FIBRILLATION**

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Introduction. Paroxysmal atrial fibrillation (AF) is a progressive heart rhythm disorder. Among the prognostic markers of increased arrhythmia paroxysms, an important role belongs to the symptoms of depression, manifested by changes in psycho-emotional state. Brought, these symptoms increase the risk of death in patients, however, data on the connection with the incident AF is relatively limited.

The **purpose** of the study is aimed to study the dynamics of depression and quality of life in patients with a paroxysmal form of AF.

Materials and methods. The study sample included 61 patients with paroxysmal form AF, divided into 4 subgroups, depending on the method of treatment. Data were collected through an interview using the PHQ-9 questionnaire to identify depressive disorders and the quality of life scale.

Results. According to the PHQ-9 scale in the standard treatment group present, the figure differed significantly from the value before treatment with (8.07 ± 0.98) points to (4.73 ± 0.50) points ($p_1 < 0.01$), $(\Delta = 41.39)$. Under the influence of standard treatment + mebicar noted, that level of depression was significantly lower than the initial values, as in 2 weeks and 1.5 months, and this decrease was 81.92% and 75.52%. Evaluating indicators of depression in the group of standard treatment with carvedilol there was a significant increase in depression by 69% compared with the value after 1.5 months of treatment ($p_2 < 0.01$). The group of standard treatment with carvedilol + mebicar revealed a decrease in depression before treatment by 34.03%, and in 2 weeks and 1.5 months by 59.68% and 38.88%, respectively.

Definitely that in the group of standard treatment there were no significant changes in the indicators of quality of life neither before treatment nor after 2 weeks or 1.5 months. Inclusion in the standard treatment of mebicar contributed to a significant increase after 2 weeks of treatment to assess the quality of life at 72.5%, and in 1.5

months at 86.83%. In the group of patients who used carvedilol, the percentage of significant changes in quality of life after 2 weeks of treatment increased by 25% ($p_1 < 0.01$), and after 1.5 months by 27% ($p_2 < 0.01$). Patients who combined treatment with carvedilol and mebicar noted that after 2 weeks of treatment their scores increased in quality of life - from (17.27 ± 0.70) points to (31.14 ± 1.12) points ($p_1 < 0.001$) and after 1.5 months from (18.40 ± 0.52) points to (31.14 ± 1.12) points ($p_2 < 0.001$). In this group, the level of quality of life increased after 2 weeks by 80.31%, and after 1.5 months by 69.23%, respectively.

Dynamics of indicators of quality of life in the standard treatment group did not find credible changes. Inclusion in the standard treatment of mebicar contributed to a significant increase after 2 weeks of treatment to assess the quality of life by 72.5%, and after 1.5 months by 86.83%. In the third group, the percentage of significant changes in quality of life after 2 weeks of treatment increased by 25% ($p_1 < 0.01$), and after 1.5 months by 27% ($p_2 < 0.01$). In the group of standard treatment + carvedilol + mebicar the quality of life increased after 2 weeks by 80.31%, and after 1.5 months by 69.23%.

Conclusion. Score reduction of depression on a scale PHQ-9 was significantly reduced in the dynamics of treatment in all study groups patients. At the same time reduction of heavy, expressed is noted, and moderate to minimal depression its manifestations. According to the scale of quality of life assessment, there was an improvement in the quality of life in groups with additional intake of anxiolytics and in combination with β -blockers.